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A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE ATTITUDE TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE ITS EFFECT ON EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT IN PRIVATE COLLEGES

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Abstract:

Organizations are expected to enhance their capacity to establish employee are provided with the basic support for the acceptance for change initiative. this study explores the attitude of employee towards organizational change through review of related literature and discourse how attitudinal factors relate to organization change. The interact antecedents of any factor and its influence on employee commitment. They are the purpose of the present study is to add a different way of looking and working with organizational change key focusing on individual emotions and personality traits. Employee commitment three component modal of commitment to in organization change. affective, normative, and continuance. Employee support organizational change researches have focused on various attitudinal constructs that represent employee attitude toward change. The constructs which frequently serve as key variable in these studies include change in attitude the performance readiness for change, commitment change, openness change, about organizational change. The mainly focus on sampling techniques are used the convenient sampling. Research tool the research instruments adopted was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was based on their private college Trichy. Statistical tool i) Percentage analysis ii) chi-square test iii) correlation test.

Keywords: Organizational Change; Employee Attitude; Employee Commitment.

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1. Introduction

Organizations are continually faced with challenges in other to compete dramatically with the global environments so change in the structure , processes and individual with the work place are planned strategized and implemented to successfully meets up with the global demand(Fuchs and prouska2014) employees can be prepared to accept change as they are central implement of the change schedule and which in turn bring about commitment of employee's to the organization.

Employee attitude towards organization and place priority on active system to prepare employees for organizational change, employee will accept high level of commitment to the organization. that are implementing unified change alike as total quality management, business process reengineering, or learning organizations concurrently change their structure, system and processes to improve their efficiency, innovative, the quality of their offerings. The beliefs have positive and negative valences for the individual are group. The system plays a dual role in attitude theory, because lower level (emotion, beliefs, and values) cause the attitude. At the same time, emotions, beliefs, and expense can be seen as part of the attitude itself. This research is useful here, because it helps identify what change in conduct are likely to underlie the formation of an attitude toward change. Results indicated that there is a weak, but important, positive relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment in both academic and supportive staff. The various capacity of organizational commitment has direct effects on various attitude toward organizational change.

In studies that have examined the situation in which employee support organizational change, researchers have focused on different attitudinal constructs that represent employees' attitude towards organizational change. Those late advance include new approaches to both the conceptual of employee commitment and the particular human resource practice intended to increase it. Mainly focuses on covenant sampling using this topic on employee attitude towards organizational change and its effect on employee commitment.

2. Need of the Study

- To understand the change in employee's commitment to that of the organization change
- To measure the employees attitude level and change in their commitment
- To understand the factors which influence the change in employee's commitment

3. Literature Review

Adeniji C.G(2017) these factors include preparation for change, responsibility to change, openness to change and pessimism about authoritative change. Abdullah Ramadhan (2017) employee commitment to organization is described with causal relation toward corporate culture which is decomposed into the dimension of teamwork communication training development and reward recognition. Wim j. ninjas (1998) commitment is strongly connected with colleagues and the style of management and could be seen as an important asset of the learning company.

Haydn Bennet, Mark Durkin (2000) Evidence from the exploratory research is presented which suggests that major change may result in the dissolution of internalised commitment part of employee. John p. Meyer E. S. Srinivas (2018) the commitment to the organization and to the change initiative both relate significantly to behavioural support. But commitment change would account for a greater proportion of variance organization we conducted two one hierarchical analysis other one regression analyses. Dr. Suresh Poojary (2018) in order to achieve the objective of ensuring commitment among employee it is employee its necessary positive attitude better working conditions and maintain cordial relationship. Maria vakola (2003) finding provide several implications both for research and practice within the organization context of change and attitude to change conformal of personality to organization change.

Ellen .M (2000) I explore individual level hypotheses using hierarchical linear regression and cross level hypotheses using hierarchical linear modelling. Loannis Nikolaos (2005) this approach organizational screening tool which among other things measure workplace stress and organizational commitment and attitude towards organizational change. Saria khatoun and Dr. Ayesha Farooq (2015) the attitude of employee toward change and organizational performance were positive the variable in the study were validated using a qualitative case study method.

Dhanalaishmi. S (2015) employee committed to the organization are valuable resource of organization four factors such as commitment organization, to the top management immediate super visors and to work group. Dr. Liz jones (2008) the study employee was experiencing large scale organizational change to the redevelopment of the hospital site the change included a move in new hospital building downswing staff prior move reduction bed and patient members and implement of multi-disciplinary team. Steven M. Elias (2007) A review of the psychological and organizational behaviour literature points out that i) internal work motivation ii) Ability to change a learning opportunity can be thought growth need strength. Iii) internal locus of control importance to how employee cope with organizational change.

Rune lines (2008) Attitude strength is an important dimension for three reason i) strength is deterrent of the relationship between the attitude object and the attitude ii) influence the consistency of response when the attitude itself is activated iii) the tension produced by an attitude that needs to be reduced by subsequent behaviour of attitude toward organizational change. John p. Meyer (2004) literature have been reviewed recently with providing general theoretical framework motivation and employee commitment.

4. Objective of the Study

- To find the organisational change incurred in recent years.
- To measure the change in employee attitude with respect to the organisational change.
- To analyse the level of employee commitment.
- To identify the gap in commitment level.

5. Scope of the Study

- The present study is confined to employee attitude towards organizational change private Arts and science college in Trichy.
- They study covers they private college faculty members

6. Factors Influence in Employee Attitude Towards Organizational Change and Its Effect on Employee Commitment

1) Organizational Change

Organizational change is the movement of an organization from one state to affairs to another. A change in the working place often requires change with in organization operating within that environment. organizational change can take many forms. It may contain a change in a organizations structure, strategy, policies, procedures, technology, or culture change management indication of decisions, planning for them need to manage the decision.

i) Organizational Structure

Organizational structure affects organizational action and arrange the foundation on with standard operating procedures and routines sit down. an organizational structure how activities comparable as task allocation coordination, and supervision are directed toward the achievement of organizational aims. Organizational structure allows the disclose allocation of responsibilities for different function and processes to various entities such as the division, department, workgroup ang individual

ii) Work force

individually specialize in identifying and recruiting technical, skilled workers and professionals if yours looking for a technical job in all of the Asian sub-continent countries, our network of clients gives you unequalled opportunities for professional growth. The total number of employees in a different undertaking called the work force

iii) Technology

constantly change is motivated the rapid developments in technology. Machinery and equipment developed from the application of scientific knowledge into the practical aims of human life or, as it is frequently expression to, they change in work.

iv) Working hours

Standard working hours the enact to limit the working hours per day, per week, per month or per year. Employee needs to work overtime, the employer will need to pay overtime payments to employee as required in the law.

v) Change in internal environment

The internal environment of any organization to events, factors, people, system, structures, along with condition inside the organization so that is generally under the control of the organization change in the leadership style, the organizations mission, or culture can accept a considerable impact on the organization.

2) Employee Attitude

“Attitude is a mental and neural state of readiness organized through experience , exerting a directive or dynamic influence beginning with the individual response to full objects and situations with which it is related suchated” attitude is a psychological state of mind in work place , employee can have each of two an positive or negative attitude about specific work task. Attitude basically include characteristics aforesaid a interest in job. working after constant supervision, taking a positive dimension of things always ahead of the game and lastly, employee willingness to contribute. Attitude can be characterized in three way first they tend to persist unless something is done to change them. Second, attitude can fall anywhere along a from very favourable to very unfavourable. Third attitude is directed toward some object about that an person has feelings and beliefs.

3) Employee Commitment

Employee commitment plays a vital role in the development of all and every organization all over the world. employee motivation, employee engagement, employee loyalty and employee communication are again some of the factors important in any organization towards achieving their objective a state of emotional and intellectual involvement that employee acquire in an organization spend to a greater success.

Change in attitude

Organizational level factors	Individual level factors	Employee attitude to change
Reshaping capabilities open system work place adaptable organization structure supportive work environment clan culture flexible organization policies and procedures	Identification with organization perceived organizational culture perceived social relations trust in colleagues and leadership competence for change self-efficacy for change	Readiness to change
Sharing of change information participative decision-making successful history of change	Trust in senior management internal locus of control need foe achievement exposure to change in the past perceived quality of shared information self-efficacy for change	Openness to change
Organizational inducement transformational leadership clan culture adequate infrastructure	Psychological resilience supervisor subordinate relationship satisfaction with human resource practices	commitment to change

change alignment with organization mission change appropriateness	perceived fairness of change job role motivation self-efficacy for change	
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4) Gab in Employee Commitment

study investigated organizational commitment with in subpopulation of the newly restructured in the private arts and science college in Trichy using an established survey instrument. Identify the gab in employee commitment to analysis. the finding revealed that an employee's tenure and work location influence commitment levels among the sample that was surveyed. This study also begin that a commitment gab exists between the expressed commitment to the current state of the organization and commitment. improve the moderate levels of organizational commitment direct reduce the commitment gab and add to the employer to employee relationship they measuring gab in commitment level.

7. Research Methodology

Research include shaping and redefining issues, formulating hypothesis or advised solution; assembling, organizing and evaluating data; creating deduction and reaching conclusion; and ultimately rigorously testing the conclusions to work out whether they fit the formulating hypothesis.

Methodology indicates a particular technique for gathering and examination of information. it is an approach to methodically take care of the examination issue. it is vital for the scientist to know the exploration strategies / procedures yet in addition strategy.

Research methodology is a way to deal with proficiently deal with the investigation issue. It may be appreciated as a specialty of looking at how ask about is done deductively. in it we think about the distinctive advance that are ordinarily gotten by an expert in considering his examination issue nearby the basis behind them. it is essential for the researcher to know the investigation methodologies / techniques yet also framework.

Research Design

A research design is to represent a way how to approach our research and condition for collection and analysis of the data to combine relevance to research purpose.

Research Method

In the project sampling it is done on the basis of non-probability sampling method. Among the non-probability sampling design chosen is convenient sampling.

Convenient sampling is where you include people who are clear to reach. For example, you could survey people. Sampling method so that relies on data collection from population members who are conveniently available to participate in study. questions can be mentioned as a popular as convenient sampling.

Sample Size

Individual understand a group of conditionals that are selected from the general population and is considered a representative of the real population for that specific study the are employee is who convenient so particular employee the collected data sample size 125

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Questionnaire is sent to the people worried about a solicitation to reply and restore the poll. Survey comprises of a number inquiry includes both explicit and general in queries identified with representative’s conduct. I have used simple percentage analysis and chi square test and correlation test

Tools Used

Research tool

The research instruments adopted was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was based on their private college Trichy

Statistical tool

The statistical tools used for this study are the following

- i) Percentage analysis ii) chi-square test iii) correlation test

i) Percentage analysis

Case Processing Summary						
Cases	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Change in workplace * qualification	20	100.0%	0	0.0%	20	100.0%

Change in workplace * Qualification Crosstabulation					
Count		Qualification			Total
		PG	Professional	PhD	
Change in workplace	strongly agree	2	0	1	3
	agree	2	1	5	8
	neutral	2	3	4	9
Total		6	4	10	20

Case Processing Summary						
Cases	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
satisfied with your work * age	20	100.0%	0	0.0%	20	100.0%

Satisfied with your Work * age Crosstabulation						
Count		age				Total
		below 30 years	31 to 40	41to50	above	
Satisfied with your work	strongly agree	2	4	2	0	8
	agree	3	3	2	0	8
	neutral	1	0	1	1	3
	disagree	0	1	0	0	1
Total		6	8	5	1	20

Case Processing Summary						
Cases	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Skills and knowledge to make this change work * experience	20	100.0%	0	0.0%	20	100.0%

Skills and knowledge to make this change work * experience Crosstabulation						
Count		Experience				Total
		below 10 years	5 to 10 years	10 to 15 years	above 15 years	
Skills and knowledge to make this change work	strongly agree	2	3	3	1	9
	agree	2	0	1	2	5
	neutral	2	0	2	1	5
	disagree	1	0	0	0	1
Total		7	3	6	4	20

ii) Chi square Analysis

Chi square test for work load and age

HO: There is no relationship between work load and age

HO: There is relationship between work load and age

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
age * workload challenging	20	100.0%	0	0.0%	20	100.0%

Count		Workload				Total
		strongly agree	agree	Neutral	disagree	
Age	below 30 years	1	3	1	1	6
	31 to 40	1	4	1	2	8
	41to50	1	3	1	0	5
	above	0	0	1	0	1
Total		3	10	4	3	20

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.781 ^a	9	.762
Likelihood Ratio	5.684	9	.771
Linear-by-Linear Association	.009	1	.923
N of Valid Cases	20		

a. 16 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .15.

chi-square Thus the result concluded that is H1 is accepted. Hence there is relationship between the work load and age

iii) Correlation Analysis

1) Correlation between age and satisfied with work

HO: $p=0$, There is no relationship between age and satisfied with work

HO: $p \neq 0$, There is relationship between age and satisfied with work

i) Correlations			
		age	Satisfied with work
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.540
	N	20	20
Satisfied with work	Pearson Correlation	.146	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.540	
	N	20	20

Thus, the result is concluded that p is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the age and satisfied with work

2) correlation between employee promotion and age

HO: $p=0$, There is no relationship between employee promotion and age

HO: $p \neq 0$, There is relationship between employee promotion and age

ii) Correlations			
		age	employee promotion decision
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	.062
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.796
	N	20	20
Employee promotion decision	Pearson Correlation	.062	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.796	
	N	20	20

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Thus, the result is concluded that p is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the employee promotion and age.

8. Conclusion

This study explores the attitude of employee towards organizational change through review of related literature and discourse how attitudinal factors relate to employee commitment. they are purpose of the present study and working with organizational change key focusing on individual emotions and personality traits. employee commitment level identify the performance. The mainly focus on sampling techniques are used the convenient sampling. the questionnaire was based on their private college Trichy. Statistical tool i) Percentage analysis ii) chi-square test iii) correlation test. chi-square Thus, the result concluded that is H1 is accepted. Hence there is relationship between the workload and age. correlation test 1) Thus, the result is concluded that p is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the age and satisfied with work. 2)

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) Thus, the result is concluded that p is greater than 0. Hence there is positive relationship exist among the employee promotion and age.

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